

Asphalt Innovation Symposium 2025

December 11
Antwerp

University of Antwerp
| SuPAR | Sustainable Pavements
and Asphalt Research

University
of Antwerp

Session 2C Emissions

Photocatalytic Asphalt Pavement for Emission
Reduction

Ali Zain Ul Abadeen, Seyed Reza Omranian, Sammy
Verbruggen, Cedric Vuye

UAntwerpen

Background

- Largest source of NOx in Europe is the road transport sector
- In 2017 transportation sector contributed approximately 40% NOx emission in EU countries
- 107,626 pre-mature deaths from NOx emissions
- NO₂ concentrations are higher in the urban areas

Annual premature deaths attributable to on-road diesel vehicle NOx emissions, 2015

*Counts only those premature deaths resulting from NOx emissions produced in the other regions shown here.

■ NOx within regulated limits
 ■ Excess NOx from trucks and buses
 ■ Excess NOx from cars and vans

Why should you care about Emissions?

- **Detrimental effects**
 - Individual level (health problems, 6.67 million death)
 - Local level (Lower visibility, Urban heat island effect, building deterioration, Acid rain, AQI index etc.)
 - Global (Climate change)

A “Pyramid of Effects” from Air Pollution

What are sources of traffic emissions?

Incomplete fuel combustion results in release of pollutants.

Gasoline Engines

Diesel Engines

Photocatalysis: A prospective solution

How the Technology Works

- **The Catalyst:** Titanium Dioxide coating applied to the road surface.

- **The Process:**

1. **Activation:** UV light hits the coating.

2. **Reaction:** The catalyst converts harmful Nitrogen Monoxide (NO) and Nitrogen Dioxide (NO₂) into harmless Nitrates.

3. **Removal:** Rainwater washes the nitrates away.

- **Important parameters:**

Pollutant concentration, UV intensity, and humidity

Objectives

- To evaluate the effect of key parameters like inlet concentration, UV intensity, and humidity on NOx degradation.
- To determine the environmental impacts from coating against air quality benefits.

Life cycle assessment (LCA)

- LCA of photocatalytic asphalt coatings using EN 15804 and ISO 14040 standards.
- Covers production and use phases (A1–A5, B1) for 1 m² of coating
- Determine the "environmental break-even point" where NO_x removal outweighs the coating's production impact.

Module	Process	Unit	Amount	Database Ecoinvent
A1	TiO ₂	kg	0.06	TiO ₂ (Anatase+rutile)
	Ethanol	kg	0.32	Ethanol, without water, in 95% solution state, from fermentation ethanol production from sugar beet molasses
A3	Electricity	kWh	2.03	Electricity, medium voltage
A2+A4	Transport	t.km	0.037	Transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, EURO6
A5	Machine	h	0.00016	Machine operation, diesel, >= 74.57 kW, high load factor

Environmental impact assessment

- Environmental impact assessment was conducted in accordance with EN 15804:2012+A2 standard.
- A single score (SS) index consolidated the environmental impact assessment according to the Environmental Footprint (EF 3.0) methodology.

Impact categories

CLIMATE CHANGE

WATER USE

LAND USE

ACIDIFICATION

OZONE DEPLETION

HUMAN TOXICITY NON-CANCER

EUTROPHICATION MARINE

ECOTOXICITY FRESHWATER

RESOURCE USE MINERALS AND METALS

HUMAN TOXICITY CANCER

EUTROPHICATION TERRESTRIAL

IONISING RADIATION

RESOURCE USE FOSSILS

PARTICULATE MATTER

EUTROPHICATION FRESHWATER

PHOTOCHEMICAL OZONE FORMATION

Experimental findings

➤ **Low Inlet Concentration (100 ppb):**

At 100 ppb NO, 15 W/m² UV, and 35% RH, the TiO₂ coating provided a relatively high NO removal efficiency of 37.70%.

➤ **High Inlet Concentration (1000 ppb):**

At 1000 ppb NO, under the same conditions (15 W/m² UV and 35% RH), the removal efficiency significantly decreased to 12.60%.

Experimental findings

➤ **Low UV intensity (5 W/m²):**

At 5 W/m² UV, 100 ppb NO, and humidity 35%, the TiO₂ coating achieved a NO removal of 25.64%.

➤ **High UV intensity (15 W/m²):**

At 15 W/m² UV, under the same conditions (100 ppb NO and humidity 35%), the NO removal efficiency increased to 37.70%.

Experimental findings

- At 35% RH, 100 ppb NO_x, and 15 W/m² UV, the TiO₂ coating achieved a NO removal of 37.70%.
- At 65% RH, under the same conditions (100 ppb NO_x and 15 W/m² UV), the NO removal efficiency decreased moderately to 32.68%.
- High humidity results:
 - ↑ Water layer
 - ↓ Interaction of NO and TiO₂

Break even analysis

-“Break-even point” occurs at **1.27 years**.

-This is the time need for air quality benefits (NO_x removal) to fully offset the initial environmental burden.

-Reduction in **Particulate Matter (PM)** emissions, Ecotoxicity (**ETP**), **Acidification (AP)**, and **Human Toxicity (HTP-non-cancer)**

Conclusion

- UV light has positive effect in pollutant degradation while pollutant concentration and humidity have negative effect.
- Approximately 1.3 years are needed for air quality benefits (NO_x removal) to fully offset the coating burden.
- Reduction of **Particulate Matter (PM)** emissions, **Ecotoxicity (ETP)**, **Acidification (AP)**, and **Human Toxicity (HTP-non-cancer)**.

Ali Zain Ul Abadeen
AliZainUl.Abadeen@uantwerpen.be

